

Benzopyrans. Part-XXVII¹. Synthesis of 2-Methyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde and 3(5)-Salicyloylpyrazole from 2-Unsubstituted 4-Oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde

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Manuscript received 14 February 1990, accepted 30 March 1990

The fused 1-pyrazoline (3), prepared from diazomethane and the acetal (2) corresponding to 4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde (1; R = H, Me, Cl and Br) gives exclusively the acetal (4) on being refluxed in toluene but a mixture of the acetal (4) and 3(5)-salicyloylpyrazole (9) on neat pyrolysis at 160–70°. The pyrazole (9) also results exclusively from percolation of a solution of the pyrazoline (3) in ethyl acetate through a column of Brockman neutral alumina. Acid-catalysed deacetalisation of the acetal (4) affords the title aldehyde (5).

PREVIOUSLY we reported^a the conversion of 4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde (trivial name: 3-formylchromone) (1a) to its 2-methyl homologue (5a) and 3(5)-salicyloylxanthone (9a). Similar conversion of 5-substituted-3-formylchromones (1b–d) to the corresponding 2-methyl homologues (5b–d) and 3(5)-(5-substituted 2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (9b–d) is described in details in this communication.

The sequence of reactions involved in the conversion of 3-formylchromone to its 2-methyl homologue is shown in Scheme 1. Acetalisation of the aldehyde (1)³ with ethylene glycol gave the dioxolane (2; Table 1). Diazomethane underwent regio- and stereo-selective addition to the pyran

2,3-double bond of 2 resulting the fused 1-pyrazoline (3; Table 2). The pmr spectrum of 3, in particular the nature of the peaks arising due to its H_A, H_B and H_X protons, deserves special mention. Both H_X and H_B appear as doublets whereas H_A appears as a doublet of a doublet with J_{AB} 18 and J_{AX} 55 Hz. This spectral feature is characteristic of an ABX system which is very often provided by a fused 1-pyrazoline⁴ where the dihedral angle for H_B and H_X is very close to 90° (J_{BX} ~ 0). The pyrazoline (3) survived crystallisation from ethyl acetate but on refluxing in toluene underwent concerted electrocyclic nitrogen extrusion and hydrogen migration yielding the 2-methylated chromone (4), the latter on treatment with aqueous acid yielded the title aldehyde (5) (Table 1). The reported^a physical data of 2a, 4a and 5a are incorporated in Table 1 and those of 3a in Table 2 for the sake of comparison with their respective analogues.

When the pyrazoline (3) was heated neat at 160–70°, the product 4 was admixed with a little quantity of the pyrazole (9; Table 3). Exclusive formation of compound 4 by refluxing the pyrazoline (3) in toluene even in the presence of a radical initiator like AIBN indicates that the conversion 3→9 does not involve any radical mechanism. At high temperature isomerisation of 1-pyrazoline (3) to the corresponding 2-pyrazoline (6) competes to some extent with its electrocyclic nitrogen elimination in concert with hydrogen migration (→4) and the 2-pyrazoline intermediate by ionic elimination of the dioxolane moiety with concomitant opening of the pyran moiety gives the ionic species 7 and 8; the latter (8) collapses to the olefin (10) (or any polymer thereof) by elimination of proton that is captured by the oxyanion

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) HOCH₂CH₂OH, PTS; (ii) CH₂N₂; (iii) C₆H₅Me, Δ; (iv) H⁺, H₂O.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 1-BENZOPYRANS (2, 4 AND 5)

Compd. no.	Yield %	M p. °C	δ (CDCl ₃)					
			H _a (s)	O(CH ₂) ₂ O (m)	Benzopyran			6-Me (s)
					2-H/Me (s)	5-H ^a	6,7,8-H ^a	
2a	85	127	6.04	4.07	8.13	8.27	7.78-7.28	-
2b	87	142	6.04	4.06	8.10	8.00	7.54-7.28	2.44
2c	85	130	6.04	4.08	8.15	8.21	7.68-7.46	-
2d	89	108	6.04	4.16	8.12	8.36	7.84-7.32	-
4a	77 (70) ^b	148	6.28	4.10	2.48	8.20	7.76-7.36	-
4b	72 (56) ^b	120	6.26	4.12	2.50	7.96	7.46-7.20	2.42
4c	75 (62) ^b	153	6.22	4.08	2.52	8.12	7.60-7.24	-
4d	82 (75) ^b	154	6.26	4.10	2.54	8.16	7.60-7.22	-
5a	88	142	10.81	-	2.72	8.52	7.62-7.48	-
5b	85	176	10.54	-	2.76	8.00	7.52-7.30	2.46
5c	92	181	10.50	-	2.76	8.18	7.66-7.20	-
5d	95	184	10.56	-	2.76	8.40	7.66-7.18	-

^a Normal aromatic splitting ^b Yield obtained by pyrolysing the pyrazoline (3) neat.

TABLE 2 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. no.	Yield %	M p. °C ^a	δ (CDCl ₃)						
			8-H ^b	5,6,7-H ^b	H _a (s)	H _B ^c	H _X ^d	H _A ^e	O(CH ₂) ₂ O (m)
3a	80	150	7.94	7.60-6.80	5.84	5.18	5.02	4.82	3.92
3b ^e	84	137	7.74	7.30-6.70	5.82	5.12	4.96	4.72	3.90
3c	86	144	7.89	7.46-6.80	5.83	5.17	5.00	4.79	3.90
3d	87	139	8.24	7.42-6.78	5.84	5.18	5.00	4.76	3.92

^a Melting is accompanied by decomposition ^b Normal aromatic splitting. ^c J_{AB} 18 Hz. ^d J_{AX} 5.5 Hz; J_{BX} 0.0 Hz. ^e 7-Me appeared as a singlet at δ 2.28.

TABLE 3 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 9*

Compd no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	δ (CDCl ₃)						
			OH	Pyrazole 3-H	H _a	R	H _b	Pyrazole 4-H	H _c
9a	8	113	12.08	8.36	7.78	-	-	-	6.80
9b	7	139	11.88	8.24	7.76	2.36	7.34	6.98	6.94
9c	10	158	11.96	8.70	7.68	-	7.44	7.04	6.98
9d	6	175	12.08	8.70	7.74	-	7.46	7.02	6.94

*In the pmr spectra NH proton could not be detected, OH proton that appeared as a broad singlet was exchangeable with D₂O, pyrazole 3-H and 4-H appeared as doublets with $J \sim 2$ Hz, and aromatic protons showed normal splitting pattern

(7) to give the salicyloylpyrazole (9) (Scheme 2). The type of fragmentation as envisaged here finds an analogy in the reported ionic cleavage of the 1,2-bond of a ketalised ketone having a nucleofugal group at 3-position⁵. The pyrazole (9) was obtained in a better yield (~15%) by percolating a solution of the fused pyrazoline (3) in ethyl acetate through a column of Brockman neutral alumina. The yield of the pyrazole (9) can evidently be further improved by repeating the process. The pyrazole (9c) on warming with pyridine-acetic anhydride formed a diacetyl derivative, possibly with the

1-acetyl-5-(2-acetoxybenzoyl)pyrazole structure. Treatment of the pyrazoline (3) in benzene with either boron trifluoride etherate or anhydrous aluminium chloride brought about extensive degradation of the substrate and none of the two products (4 and 9) could be isolated.

Experimental

The recorded m ps. are uncorrected and all the new compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. Pmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a

Jeol JNM-FX-100 spectrophotometer with SiMe₄ as internal reference. Light petroleum refers to the fraction with b p 60–80°.

2-(4-Oxo 4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-1,3-dioxolane(2) : Reaction of the aldehyde (1; 20 mmol) with ethylene glycol (22 mmol) in refluxing dry benzene (100 ml) containing *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (50 mg) as previously described⁶, afforded the dioxolane (2; Table 1).

3a, 9a-Dihydro-9a-(1, 3-dioxolan-2-yl)-9-oxo-3H, 9H-[1]benzopyrano[3,2-c] pyrazole (3) : An ethereal solution of diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (3 g) was added to the acetal (2; 6 mmol) dissolved in dichloromethane (25 ml) and the reaction mixture was kept at 4° for 2–3 days. Subsequent evaporation of the solvent from the mixture and crystallisation of the residue from ethyl acetate furnished the pyrazole (3; Table 2).

2-(2-Methyl-4 oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-1,3-dioxolane (4) : The 1-pyrazoline (3; 2 mmol) was refluxed in toluene (25 ml) in the absence or presence of AIBN (5–10 mg) for 4–6 h. The mixture was then concentrated, diluted with light petroleum and allowed to cool when the dioxolane (4) crystallised out, which was further crystallised (charcoal) from benzene-light petroleum (Table 1).

2-Methyl-4-oxo 4H-1-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde (5) : A solution of the dioxolane (4; 1 mmol) in methanol (7 ml), water (3 ml) and sulphuric

acid (2 drops) was warmed for 10 min, then diluted with water and extracted with chloroform. The material obtained after usual work-up of the chloroform extract was crystallised from chloroform-light petroleum to afford the aldehyde (5; Table 1).

Pyrolysis of the pyrazole (3) : The 1-pyrazoline (3; 2 mmol) was put portionwise into a flask heated in an oil-bath at 160–70° when the compound melted with evolution of nitrogen. After the whole amount of the compound (3) had melted, it was heated at the aforesaid temperature for further 15 min, then cooled, dissolved in benzene and extracted with 10% sodium hydroxide (3 × 10 ml). The benzene extract after usual work-up gave the dioxolane (4).

The aforesaid alkali extract was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract after treatment with charcoal was concentrated to afford 3(5)-salicyloylpyrazole (9) as yellow crystals (Table 3). The pyrazole (9c) on warming with pyridine-acetic anhydride gave 1-acetyl-5-(2-acetoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)pyrazole as light yellow crystals, m.p. 75° (benzene-light petroleum); δ 8.26 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, pyrazole 3-H), 7.86 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, PhH *ortho* to Cl and CO), 7.50 (1H, dd, *J* 8, 2 Hz, PhH *ortho* to Cl and *para* to CO), 7.14 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, PhH *ortho* to OAC), 6.96 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, pyrazole 4-H), 2.68 (3H, s, NCOMe) and 2.12 (3H, s, OCOMe).

Percolation of the pyrazoline (3) through alumina : The pyrazoline (3a; 1.30 g 5 mmol) dissolved in ethyl acetate (10 ml) was adsorbed over Brockman neutral alumina (30 g) contained in a column (1 cm i.d.) and the material eluted with ethyl acetate. The first few fractions contained the unchanged pyrazoline (3a) whereas the last few fractions after concentration furnished the pyrazole (9a; 120 mg, 13%). The other three pyrazoles (9b–d) were obtained in 16, 16 and 18% yield respectively by similar treatment of the appropriate pyrazoline (3).

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from C.S.I.R., New Delhi is duly acknowledged.

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